

Citizen Science

Scan 2025

Landscape and evolution
of citizen science in Belgium

Scivil

Colophon

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Summary

The Citizen Science Scan examines active citizen science initiatives in Belgium (reference year 2025).

What is citizen science?

Citizen science is scientific research that is partially or entirely conducted by non-scientists (citizens), often in collaboration with or supervised by professional scientists.

Key findings

Number of projects

- In 2025, there were 242 active citizen science projects in Belgium, a strong increase compared to 2023 (n=150). This increase reflects both improved search strategies and a genuine rise in new projects supported by regional and European funding.
- 2024 stood out as a remarkable peak year for newly launched citizen science projects.
- Half of the surveyed projects have a duration of two to five years.

Citizen science in schools

- 38% of citizen science projects collaborate with schools.
- Students primarily collect data but are increasingly involved in other activities such as co-designing the protocol, analysing data, disseminating results and formulating recommendations.

Topics

- 40% of the projects conduct research on biodiversity and biology. Other projects focus on climate and environment (19%), human behaviour and well-being (18%), archaeology, history and heritage (17%), and exact and technical sciences (6%).
- The most notable increase is in projects related to healthcare and health sciences, driven by regional and European incentives.

Language

- In most projects (83%), citizens can participate in Dutch. This is substantially more than in English (47%), French (38%) or German (12%).
- The number of multilingual projects has increased compared to 2023. Half of the projects now offer more than one language.

Activities

- Compared to 2023, citizens are more frequently involved in different research phases of the project, particularly in projects focusing on human behaviour and well-being, and climate and environment.

Participants

- Citizen science projects in archaeology, history and heritage typically work with smaller teams (up to 100 people). In other topics, project sizes vary, ranging from less than 20 to more than 20,000 participants.
- The majority of projects have a regional scope (taking place in one of the regions or communities in Belgium).

Initiators	Partners	Funders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most projects are initiated by a government body (38%) or a non-profit organisation (31%), followed by universities and colleges (26%). • Eight in ten projects are led by an organisation with a research mandate. This represents an increase compared to 2023. 		

Conclusions and recommendations

The Citizen Science Scan 2025 shows a citizen science landscape that has continued to grow and diversify since 2023. Citizen participation is becoming broader and more in-depth: in addition to data collection, citizens are increasingly involved in other phases of the research process. New domains such as healthcare, biomedical sciences and the social sciences and humanities are clearly on the rise, while traditional strongholds such as biodiversity, heritage and the environment continue to perform well.

These developments demonstrate that consistent policy choices and regional support are making an impact. Nevertheless, further efforts are needed to make this growth sustainable. We recommend providing both flexible and long-term funding, strengthening the integration of citizen science into policy and organisations, and encouraging collaboration across disciplines and sectors. By involving citizens from the outset and lowering barriers to participation, citizen science can generate more and better data, while also contributing to broader public trust in science.

Foreword

When we developed the Citizen Science Scan two years ago, we made a deliberate choice from the outset. We did not only envision a deep and accurate snapshot of the Belgian citizen science landscape, but also aimed to create a monitoring tool to highlight trends and developments.

I'm happy to see that, after this second edition, several dynamics are already clearly surfacing.

Take 2024, for example. This turned out to be a record year for newly launched citizen science projects in Belgium, supported in part by European funding. Despite Europe's choice to financially incentivise citizen science, these calls remain highly competitive. So why are we doing so well?

2024 is not a coincidence. It is the result of years of consistent policy choices, both at regional, federal and European levels, and within research institutions and NGOs. Thanks to mostly Flemish regional support and support from their own organisation, initiators have been able to build experience and credibility, two crucial elements for securing European funds. In that sense, our own domestic policies have effectively created a European accelerator for Belgian citizen science.

Another trend we observed: since the previous edition, citizen science has been spreading rapidly in healthcare and the biomedical sciences. This too is the outcome of a deliberate choice towards more participatory research in the health sector. We are also seeing more project proposals emerging on food. Perhaps the VLAIO call on citizen science and food that was launched a few years ago served as an inspiration?

It is nice to see that the developments we witness in the field are clearly reflected in the data from our Citizen Science Scan. I am also very pleased with the strengthened methodology in this second edition and our collaboration with UCLouvain for data collection. This allows us to paint a much clearer picture of the citizen science landscape. It also enables all actors in Belgium to let this landscape grow and thrive through targeted policies. Because choosing citizen science is a choice for more impactful research, valued citizen expertise, and more evidence-based policies.

Annelies Duerinckx
Head of Scivil

Introduction

The Citizen Science Scan offers insight into the **current state, nature and evolution** of the citizen science landscape in Belgium. For this purpose, we identify and analyse active citizen science initiatives for a specific reference year. We conduct this scan periodically to map developments over time.

Following the first edition in 2023, this second Citizen Science Scan presents a snapshot for reference year 2025. Wherever appropriate, we compare the two editions to identify trends and shifts within the Belgian citizen science landscape.

This report includes the methodology, results, and recommendations of this inventory.

Methodology

Research

From 14 to 25 July 2025, a student team¹ conducted an online search for citizen science activities using search engines, social media, citizen science platforms and funding lists. We searched on 'citizen science' and related terms in Dutch, French and English². These search terms were logged. From 22 April to 1 September 2025, a student from UCLouvain helped mapping projects of the French-speaking region of Belgium as part of her master's thesis.

In August 2025, we also issued an open call via Scivil's newsletter and social media for citizen science projects to share information for the inventory.

From 6 October to 24 November 2025, two additional students expanded the inventory following the same protocol. They completed missing information, removed duplicates and verified whether each project met the criteria.

1. The students were selected based on the following criteria: master's level, diverse academic backgrounds, and knowledge of citizen science. The students were supervised by Scivil.

2. Search terms: burgerwetenschap, citizen science, IoT, sensoren, citizen observatory, samen meten, monitoren, crowd science, smart city, citizen engagement (in science), community science, (urban) living labs, fablab, DIY lab, open lab, science participative, science citoyenne, recherche participative, participatief onderzoek, co-creatie, crowdsourcing, crowd science, citizen sensing, grassroots science, patient-led research, patiëntenparticipatie, (Participatory) Action Research.

Consulted sources

- **Citizen Science Scan 2023:**
 - Which projects are still active?
- **Citizen science platforms:**
 - [Belspo citizen science page](#)
 - [University of Antwerp citizen science page](#)
 - [Doedat.be](#)
 - [Eu-citizen.science](#)
 - [FRIS](#)
 - [Histories vzw](#)
 - [IedereenWetenschapper](#)
 - [iNaturalist](#)
 - [Mijn Tuinlab](#)
 - [SciStarter](#)
 - [Velehanden.nl](#)
 - [Waarnemingen.be](#)
 - [Zooniverse](#)
- **Funding lists:**
 - European Commission
 - FWO
 - Horizon Europe
 - IMPETUS
 - Interreg Europe
 - VLAIO

- **Search engines:**
 - Google
 - Ecosia
- **Social media:**
 - Facebook
 - Instagram

Definition

The aim of the inventory is to provide a list of citizen science initiatives that is as exhaustive as possible. To be included, a project must meet the following criteria:

- The project aligns with Scivil's definition of citizen science;
- The project seeks to answer a research question or collects data for future research;
- The project team includes at least one Belgian partner;
- The project has an online presence related to the citizen science initiative.

How we define citizen science

Citizen science is scientific research that is entirely or partially conducted by non-professional scientists (citizens) often in collaboration with or supervised by professional scientists. The citizens who engage in citizen science are called citizen scientists. Scivil's full vision for citizen science can be found [here](#).

We consider related citizen science activities to be separate initiatives when:

- They are organised by different project teams (e.g. the digitisation of an archive at various locations by different local teams);
- They pursue different research goals (e.g. 'VespaWatch' and 'Lentevallen Aziatische hoornaar');
- They use their own websites, geographical scopes or protocols.

We also include citizen science activities that are fully carried out by individual citizens, independent of a broader initiative (e.g. individual volunteers exploring a paleontological theme). These activities often do not have an online presence, meaning they are admittedly underrepresented.

This inventory probably also underestimates the number of initiatives that do align with the definition of citizen science, but do not label themselves as such. Some projects do not use the term because they are not familiar with it, or because other terms are more commonly used in their domain. These domain-

specific names are not on our radar (yet). As a result, some initiatives are not captured in this inventory.

In addition to projects that are time-bound, we include long-term and permanent initiatives, that collect data process-wise or in project-like cycles. In some cases, it is not entirely clear whether a project is still active. Unless evidence suggests otherwise, we consider such projects to be active.

When the exact nature of citizen participation is unclear, but the project identifies itself as citizen science, we include it in the inventory.

Projects in which citizens only have to fill in a questionnaire about themselves as research subjects, are not considered citizen science. If the questionnaire is a tool that helps citizens in collecting data as citizen scientists, and if the observations concern an external phenomenon rather than the participant, the project is generally regarded as citizen science.

Not inventoried, but valued

Citizen participation takes many forms, each with its own value. When a project is not included in this inventory, this does not imply a judgement of quality or relevance. Scivil celebrates diversity and potential synergies between different forms of citizen participation. In this inventory, we focus on mapping citizen science in Belgium as precisely as possible, which means that many valuable initiatives with citizen participation are not included.

Data collection

For each citizen science project in the inventory, we recorded the following attributes:

- Name and website;
- Names of coordinating organisation and partners;
- Status (active/non-active);
- Languages of the project;
- Scientific topic;
- Description of citizen tasks and classification according to the five research phases;
- Channel through which the project was found (search term, platform, survey).

These attributes are based on the PPSR Core Standard³ and have been adjusted where necessary to fit our own context and information needs. We filled in the attributes using publicly available information and supplemented missing information from our own sources.

Finally, we asked all initiatives with online contact information to complete a survey about their project. The survey asked about the attributes listed above,

3. PPSR Core (Public Participation in Scientific Research) is a global, transdisciplinary data and metadata standard for public participation in scientific research (citizen science). This enables data to be used consistently across different platforms and projects.

as well as additional information that is difficult to retrieve online, such as funding sources, start and end dates, and geographical scope. The full survey is included as an appendix to this report.

After data collection, we analysed these attributes. The next chapter discusses the key findings.

Results

1. Number of projects

⚡ In 2024, an exceptionally large number of new projects was launched, thanks to regional and international funding.

The inventory includes 445 Belgian citizen science projects⁴, of which 242 were active during the survey period (from 22 April to 24 November 2025). Of those 242 active projects, 116 provided additional information through our survey.

4. See [Methodology - Definition](#) for the definition of a Belgian citizen science project.

Figure 1
Citizen science projects in Belgium.

The results in this report refer to the active projects (n=242). For analyses using survey data, we only use the survey sample (n=116).

Of the 242 active projects, 115 were already included in the first edition of the Citizen Science Scan. The remaining 127 projects not only include newly launched projects, but also projects that were not identified in the previous edition (see box).

Newly started projects

Figure 2
Newly started projects per year (n=116).

Since 2012, at least one new project has started every year, and since 2019, at least eight new projects have been launched annually. The oldest and longest-running citizen science initiative in Belgium dates back to 1925: the Royal Observatory engages citizens to measure the impact of earthquakes.

Newly started projects, cumulatively

Figure 3
Newly started projects per year, cumulatively⁵ (n=116).

In 2024, no fewer than 22 new projects were launched. That year, we also observe a slight increase in regionally funded initiatives and a strong increase in internationally funded projects (see [9. Funders](#)). In 2024, more universities and colleges also acted as initiators (see [7. Initiators](#)).

5. In the cumulative analysis we assume that a project didn't temporarily stop between the starting year and the reference year.

Half of all surveyed projects have a duration of 2 to 5 years. One in five projects lasts longer than 10 years. The median duration is 5 years, which is also the most common duration (16%), closely followed by 3 years (15%). The topic cluster **Biodiversity and Biology** (see [2. Topics](#)) contains the highest number of long-running projects, although every topic cluster includes at least two projects with a duration of more than ten years.

Figure 4
Number of projects by duration and topic cluster (n=116).

More projects or better search strategies?

In this second edition of the Citizen Science Scan, we identified a lot more initiatives than two years ago. There are two main reasons for this.

On the one hand, we have refined and expanded our search strategies, drawing on the experience gained during the first scan in 2023. We searched more platforms and used a broader set of search terms. Our survey also yielded more responses. Our network has grown considerably since the previous edition, and the collaboration with UCLouvain increased our reach in French-speaking Belgium. Meanwhile, the Citizen Science Scan has become well known, which encourages project coordinators to make more effort to have their project included. As a result, we are increasingly succeeding in providing a comprehensive picture of citizen science in Belgium.

On the other hand, we also observe an actual increase in citizen science initiatives in Belgium, particularly in 2024. That year, many projects were able to start thanks to regional and especially international funding, and more universities and colleges acted as initiators. Whether academia has increased its emphasis on citizen science, or whether more Belgian research projects were simply approved in international calls, can not be determined based on these data.

2. Topics

Citizen science in healthcare and biomedical sciences has grown strongly.

Figure 5
Number of projects by topic (n=242). The thin bars show the numbers in 2023.

The topic 'Biodiversity and Biology' contains the largest share of projects (40%)⁶. In this edition, almost twice as many projects were identified within this topic compared to 2023. Many new projects have recently been launched, but the refined search strategy used for this second Citizen Science Scan also contributes to the increase. In addition, projects related to biology and biodiversity often have long, sometimes even permanent durations, which means that relatively few projects come to an end.

The topic 'Archaeology, History and Heritage' ranks second once again (16%), with roughly the same number of projects as in 2023.

The most notable increase is seen in the topic 'Healthcare and Biomedical sciences' (10%), which rises from 4 to 24 projects (see box). Except for one project from 2015, all projects in this topic started in or after 2019. This makes 'Healthcare and Biomedical sciences' a particularly young topic within the citizen science landscape.

6. We categorize the 242 active citizen science projects according to the PPSR Core classification. Through the survey, we also asked project initiators to categorize their own project, as a quality check. As in the previous edition, the topics 'Biodiversity' and 'Biology: botany and zoology' were merged.

Figure 6
Number of projects by topic cluster (n=242).

To obtain a less fragmented overview, these topics were consolidated into five clusters.

The ● **Biodiversity and Biology** cluster (which almost entirely overlaps with the topic of the same name) is by far the largest category (41%). In these projects, citizen scientists primarily collect data through observations of animals (e.g., [Spincity](#), [VespaWatch](#)) or plants (e.g. [FOURCAST](#), [FloraBru](#)). This may involve counting (e.g., [Het Grote Vogelweekend](#)), taking photographs (e.g. [waarnemingen.be](#)) or annotating existing data (e.g., annotating trail camera images via [DoeDat](#)).

The next three clusters are roughly the same size.

The ● **Climate and Environment** cluster (19%) includes projects on weather observations (e.g., via the [RMI app](#) or [WOW-BE](#) sensors) and data related to climate impact and resilience (e.g., [Coastsnap Belgium](#), [Klimaat Trappers](#), [Urban ReLeaf](#)). Environmental projects also appear in this cluster, covering topics such as air quality ([Luchtpijp](#)), water quality ([Smartwater](#)), litter ([Plastic Pirates](#)), noise pollution ([De Oorzaak](#)), light pollution ([Saving Private Orion](#)) and soil quality ([Archisols](#)).

The ● **Human Behaviour and Well-Being** cluster (18%) includes human-oriented disciplines. In the health sciences, we observe projects on infectious diseases ([TekenNet](#)), the microbiome ([Isala](#)) or bacteria ([POEMBAKterie](#)), as well as projects specifically focusing on care provision ([Van Omstaander tot Held](#), [SMARTS](#), [CAIRE](#)). In the humanities, there are cross-pollinations with sociology ([Titan](#), [Communities Against Violence](#), [VISA VIS](#)) and mobility ([Telraam](#), [Straatvinken](#)). Projects in linguistics and literary studies are often interdisciplinary, with a focus on history ([ERASMOS](#), [GezelleBron](#)) or AI ([POL](#), [Burgerpraat!](#)).

In the ● **Archaeology, History and Heritage** cluster (17%), citizen scientists primarily transcribe and annotate historical documents such as [inheritance declarations](#), [court rulings](#) and population registers (e.g. [Itinera Nova](#), [S.O.S. Antwerpen](#)). These projects are often locally organised around a specific city or region, such as the Westhoek, Aalst or the archives of the Sovereign Court of Bouillon.

The smallest cluster, ● **Exact and Technical Sciences** (6%), includes both fundamental research in, for example, physics ([AcceleROB](#)) and astronomy ([Radio Meteor Zoo](#), [Val-u-Sun](#)), and applied research on GIS systems. Half of the projects fall under GIS and cartography, serving purposes such as mobility ([Fietsbarometer](#)), history ([DigHimapper](#)) or open data ([OpenStreetMap](#)).

Figure 7
Number of projects by start year and topic cluster (n=116).

For a long time, citizen science appeared to be almost exclusively applied in nature research. From 2015 onwards, we see a diversification of research topics, with projects emerging on mobility, air quality, and an increasing number of themes within the social sciences and biomedical research.

Figure 8
Percentage of projects with additional research topics, by topic cluster (n=116).

Two out of three surveyed projects engage not only with their main topic but also with one or more additional topics. This is the case, for example, for [CAIRE](#) (AI and healthcare), [Small World of Words](#) (psychology and linguistics) and [Fietsbarometer](#) (GIS and mobility).

In the **Biodiversity and biology** cluster, half of all projects are monodisciplinary and the other half interdisciplinary. In the other four clusters, more than 60% of the projects are working with multiple topics. The **Climate and Environment** cluster leads the way, with as much as 80% interdisciplinary projects.

Figure 9
Number of projects which has a topic as additional topic (n=116).

Topics within the **Human Behaviour and Well-Being** cluster are most frequently mentioned as an additional focus (33%). Furthermore, 27% and 26% of projects have an additional focus from the **Exact and Technical Sciences** and **Climate and Environment** clusters, respectively.

Citizen science goes viral in healthcare

Citizen science in the health sciences has grown rapidly since 2019. This surge aligns with experiences in the field: citizen science has witnessed increased visibility and recognition within healthcare and the biomedical sciences for some time. The Belgian [Isala](#) project won the European Citizen Science Award, and a European working group and accompanying conference, [CS4Health](#), were established. More generally, there is growing attention to participation within this discipline, for example through patient empowerment, shared decision-making, and the recognition of experiential expertise. Citizen science aligns closely with these developments.

3. Activities

⚡ Citizens are increasingly active in multiple phases of the research process.

Citizens participate in citizen science in various ways:

- Helping define the **research question**;
- Shaping the research design or intervention through **co-creation**;
- **Data collection** (executing a protocol, installing and maintaining sensors, counting / identifying, providing data, taking a sample);
- **Data analysis**⁷ (annotating / transcribing, interpreting data);
- **Communication and dissemination** (formulating recommendations, communicating the results).

In most projects (83%), citizens participate in data collection. In the **Climate and Environment** cluster, citizens even collect data in every project (100%). The most common activities are counting and identifying, providing text and images, and conducting measurements with sensors. Compared to the Citizen Science Scan 2023, there is a strong increase in the share of projects in which citizens collect data (+14%). This is to be expected, as this edition includes substantially more projects in the **Biodiversity and Biology** cluster; in 97% of these projects, citizens take part in data collection.

In 38% of all projects, citizens also perform data analysis. In the **Archaeology, History and Heritage** cluster, citizens are involved in data analysis in 78% of the projects, by annotating or transcribing documents.

In other research phases, citizen participation is less common. However, compared with the Citizen Science Scan 2023, citizen participation has increased for defining the research question (×5), co-creation of research design (×4), and communication of research results (×7). Unlike the rise in data collection, this increase appears to reflect an actual growth in citizen involvement across these research phases in recent years. Projects in the **Human Behaviour and Well-Being** and **Climate and Environment** clusters involve citizens most frequently in multiple phases of research, with activities such as protocol co-creation, communication and formulating recommendations.

Figure 10
Percentage of projects in which citizens participate in a specific research phase (n=242). The gray hemispheres on the left show the percentages in 2023.

7. By data collection, we refer to activities in which data are only gathered. By data analysis, we refer to the interpretation of data (as opposed to pure data collection). In this context, data analysis does not refer to performing quantitative or qualitative analyses on the compiled or aggregated dataset.

Figure 11
Number of projects by number of research phases in which citizens are involved, broken down by topic cluster (n=242). The light blue bars show the percentages in 2023.

Most projects involve citizens in only one research phase. This is especially true in the **Biodiversity and Biology** cluster, where citizens typically participate only in data collection, and in the **Archaeology, History and Heritage** cluster, where they most often contribute to data analysis. In the **Climate and Environment** and especially **Human Behaviour and Well-Being** clusters, there are markedly more projects involving citizens in multiple research phases. Furthermore, we observe a strong increase in projects engaging citizens across several phases (+17%).

Going beyond counting

Data collection is by far the most prominent research phase in which citizens are involved. The scale advantage of citizen scientists in collecting and analysing data is undeniable.

At the same time, citizens are increasingly active in other research phases, something we wholeheartedly welcome. By involving citizens in the formulation of research questions, researchers can enhance the societal relevance of their work from the start, and tailor data collection to the context and abilities of the citizens. Scivil continues to support this evolution and hopes it will expand to disciplines in which citizens have so far mainly contributed to data collection or data analysis.

Figure 12
 Number of projects in which citizens participate in specific research activities, broken down by topic cluster (n=242).

4. Participants

⚡ The number of participants in citizen science projects can range from 20 to 20,000.

Figure 13
Number of participants per project (n=116).

The number of participants per project varies greatly. Nearly four in ten projects work with fewer than 100 citizens, three in ten involve between 100 and 1,000 citizens, and another three in ten have more than 1,000 participants⁸. According to the most conservative estimate, the 116 surveyed ongoing projects collectively account for at least 1,035,395 unique participations⁹.

8. The survey (n=116) gauged the number of participants using predefined answer options.

9. A unique participation refers to one citizen taking part in one citizen science project. A citizen who transcribes multiple documents for an archival project counts as one unique participation. A citizen who, in addition to taking part in an animal survey for project X, also participates in an air-sensor measurement for project Y, counts as two unique participations.

Figure 14
Number of projects by number of participants and topic (n=116).

Projects in **Archaeology, History and Heritage** typically involve fewer people. These projects are run by small teams and often focus on data collection within a small geographical area. In contrast, projects in the **Exact and Technical Sciences** cluster attract the largest numbers of participants. For example, [Radio Meteor Zoo](#) recorded 23,325 unique participations through online annotations, while [Fietsbarometer](#) reports 12,149 unique participations.

Figure 15
Number of participants per project, classified by geographical scope (n=116).

Most projects have a regional scope (covering a Belgian region or community) and vary in size. Local projects generally have fewer participants, whereas global projects involve larger numbers.

Figure 16
Number of participants per project, classified by type of participation (n=116).

In half of the projects, citizens can participate both online and offline. In the remaining half, participation is exclusively online (25%) or exclusively offline (25%). Offline projects generally attract a smaller number of participants, with the '[Grote Schelpenteldag](#)' as a notable exception, counting 11,200 participants.

More than a million

Whether citizens occasionally use a nature app or are committed to a long-term archival project, every participation represents a valuable interaction between citizens and science. This Citizen Science Scan reveals more than one million unique participations in citizen science, and this figure is the most conservative estimate based on the 116 surveyed projects.

5. Citizen science in schools

⚡ Students not only collect data, but increasingly take on analysis, communication and protocol design.

Figure 17
Projects that collaborate with schools, by topic cluster (n=44).

Of the 116 surveyed projects, 44 collaborate with schools. One in three of these school-based projects falls within the **Climate and Environment** cluster, mainly focusing on environmental topics such as air quality and litter. Schools also frequently engage with topics from the **Human Behaviour and Well-Being** cluster (25%), covering a wide range of sociocultural and behavioural themes. In contrast, projects within the health care and biomedical sciences rarely collaborate with schools, likely because they deal with sensitive data.

The **Biodiversity and Biology** cluster (23%) is the third largest category among school-related projects. Within this cluster, one in three projects collaborates with schools.

Archaeology, History and Heritage and **Exact and Technical Sciences** are smaller categories within the school-project landscape. The proportion of school collaborations within these clusters is high, but the absolute number of projects is too small to draw strong conclusions.

Figure 18
Number of projects within topic cluster that collaborate with schools (n=116).

In nearly every school-based project (42 out of 44), students collect data. In half of the projects, students also carry out data analyses. A similar amount involves students in communication and dissemination, and one quarter of school projects includes students in reflecting on the research protocol. Students are less frequently involved in formulating the research question. Compared to the previous Citizen Science Scan, students have been considerably more active

across different phases of the research process. Only in the **Biodiversity and Biology** cluster participation remains largely limited to data collection.

Figure 19
Number of projects within topic cluster that collaborate with schools, by research phase (n=44). The gray bars show the data in 2023.

Continuing to choose citizen science in schools

Between 2010 and 2018, a growing number of citizen science initiatives collaborated with schools. During that period, citizen science in schools was strongly and successfully encouraged through policy measures. Even today, there remains considerable room for growth, and the mutual benefits for both schools and citizen science initiatives are clear. Schools can develop students' research competencies using real, open scientific questions, while citizen science initiatives benefit from fresh perspectives, more data, and increased visibility.

A positive evolution within schools is the broader involvement of students throughout the research process. By engaging them in multiple research phases, students gain a deeper understanding of the scientific method, while researchers benefit from new insights and enthusiastic ambassadors.

Scivil advocates for a sustained policy commitment toward expanding citizen science in schools and is eager to support citizen science initiatives in doing so.

6. Language

Dutch is by far the largest language in the Belgian citizen science landscape.

In 83% of the projects, you can participate in Dutch. This is vastly more than English (47%), French (38%) or German (12%). The proportion of projects using English has increased, likely because this edition identified more projects with international funding.

Figure 20
Percentage of projects in which citizens can take part in a specific language (n=242).

The proportion of projects with a single working language has decreased slightly (from 56% to 45%), while the proportion of bilingual projects has risen (from 19% to 32%), mainly the combinations English–Dutch (61% of all bilingual projects) and Dutch–French (21%).

Figure 21
Percentage of projects by number of available languages (n=242).

Neighbourhood level projects always use a single working language. In regional projects, participation is usually possible in one language (68%), and less often in two (25%) or three (8%) languages. Projects at the national, international, or global level are generally mostly multilingual (89%).

Figure 22
Number of projects by geographical reach and by number of available languages (n=116).

In the **Archaeology, History and Heritage** and **Biodiversity and Biology** clusters, projects typically use a single working language. In projects on **Climate and Environment** and **Human Behaviour and Well-Being**, the number of monolingual and bilingual projects is about the same. Projects in the **Exact and Technical Sciences** cluster are predominantly multilingual.

Figure 23
Number of projects per topic, broken down by number of available languages (n=116).

Dutch vs. French

The most common language in the Belgian citizen science landscape is Dutch, but multilingualism is clearly increasing, especially in larger or internationally embedded projects. In addition to the scale level, multilingualism is also linked to thematic clusters.

Despite refined search strategies and increased attention to French-speaking Belgium, this edition again identified far fewer French-language projects than their Dutch-language counterparts. While this seemingly shows a more developed citizen science landscape in Flanders, projects in French-speaking Belgium may also be less visible as there is no central point of contact such as Scivil, or an accessible platform for citizens such as 'ledereen Wetenschapper'.

7. Initiators

⚡ Government organisations, non-profit organisations and academic institutions continue to be the most important initiators.

In four out of ten projects, a government organisation is the initiator. Non-profit organisations and academic institutions (universities and colleges) complete the top three. Privately organised and community-led projects represent only a small fraction of the Belgian citizen science landscape. However, small grassroots initiatives are more difficult to find and are therefore underrepresented in the Citizen Science Scan.

Figure 24
Initiators of Belgian citizen science projects (n=242).

The top 5 initiators are the Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Natuurpunt, the State Archives, KU Leuven and Ghent University. In the clusters **Biodiversity and Biology** and **Archaeology, History and Heritage**, the initiator is usually a government institution. In the cluster **Human Behaviour and Well-Being**, academic institutions and non-profits predominantly take the lead. In projects within **Climate and Environment** and **Exact and Technical Sciences**, ownership is distributed evenly across the three main categories.

Figure 25
Project initiators, broken down by topic cluster (n=242).

Figure 26
Initiators of Belgian citizen science projects: research institutions and other (n=242).

In eight out of ten projects, a research institution takes the lead. This is by definition the case for academic institutions, but initiators from the government and non-profit sectors also generally have a primary focus on research.

90% of the projects are led by a Belgian organisation. The remaining 10% are coordinated by a foreign organisation with at least one Belgian partner in the consortium.

Top-down vs. bottom-up initiatives

Belgium has a strong citizen science landscape, driven primarily by research-oriented government institutions, non-profits and academic partners. This is partly the result of a stimulating regional (especially Flemish) policy that actively supports citizen science and enables professionalisation.

Smaller, community-led initiatives appear far less frequently in our dataset. However, bottom-up grassroots projects also play a crucial role in the citizen science landscape: they can respond quickly, flexibly and with precision to local needs and communities.

8. Partners

⚡ Collaboration is the norm. More than 8 out of 10 projects work with at least one type of partner.

Most projects (82%) collaborate with at least one type of partner. Half of the surveyed projects work with a research partner. Government organisations (34%) and non-profit organisations (36%) are also frequently involved. These types of partners are well positioned to contribute to societal impact by implementing research results in policy or using them in advocacy efforts. 30% of projects involve an educational partner¹⁰.

¹⁰. This category was defined more broadly than in the previous Citizen Science Scan. In addition to formal educational institutions, it now also includes research-oriented partners who aim to teach citizens something through their participation, as well as partners in science communication and general communication. In this edition, there is also no separate category for communication partners.

Figure 27
Percentage of citizen science projects that collaborate with a type of partner (n=116).

Non-profits and government organisations most often collaborate with a research partner. Universities and colleges frequently involve government and non-profit organisations. Cultural partners are most commonly selected by non-profits, while collaborations with private partners occur mostly among academic initiators.

Figure 28
Percentage of citizen science projects per number of partner types (n=116).

Partners as a lever for impact

Citizen science relies on collaboration, not only between citizens and scientists, but also among a wide range of organisations.

Carefully selected partnerships largely determine the societal impact of a project. Local networks and communities broaden reach and anchor an initiative in the daily lives of citizens. Policy and civil society partners help translate research results more quickly into concrete societal change.

Each partner contributes their own expertise, from local knowledge and lived experience to scientific methodology, policy influence and data management. This creates impact that no single actor could achieve on its own.

9. Funders

⚡ Regional funding remains crucial, while European funding is rising sharply, with 2024 as a peak year.

Figure 29
Number of funding sources per project (n=116).

Two out of three projects have a single funding source. One out of three projects has at least two.

Half of the surveyed citizen science projects use their own resources. In the previous Citizen Science Scan, this was still two out of three projects. Regardless of start year, own resources remain a common funding source and form the backbone of long-running projects (15 years or more).

Figure 30
Funding sources (n=116).

43% of the projects rely on regional project funding (from Flanders, Brussels or Wallonia). Among projects starting in 2024, there is a peak in regional funding, including funders such as FWO, BOF, amai!, Brussels Environment and the Scheldemondfonds. Regardless of this peak, we see regional funding appearing frequently from projects starting in 2017.

The use of international funding has increased from 12% in 2023 to 22%, due to a remarkable spike in European funding among projects starting in 2024 (Horizon Europe, ERC, Biodiversa+, IMPETUS, EMIF, FEDER, see box). Private funding decreased from 10% to 5% and has mainly been used since 2020.

Government organisations, non-profits and academic institutions mainly use their own and regional resources. Informal organisations fund their citizen science projects through local funding, crowdfunding and own contributions.

International funding is most common among academic institutions (40%) and non-profits (36%). Belgian front-runners include the University of Antwerp, KU Leuven, VUB, the Institute of Natural Sciences and ISSeP. International funding also often goes to non-profits, particularly those with a research-oriented mission.

Federal funding for citizen science mainly goes to government organisations (58%). Regional funding is evenly distributed across government organisations, non-profits and academic institutions. Crowdfunding is used most often by non-profits and informal organisations.

Figure 31
Distribution of funding sources according to type of initiator (n=116).

The success story of European funding

In 2024, an exceptionally high number of citizen science projects started with European support. A large number of projects also began with European funding in 2025, and this number will likely be even higher in the next edition, as projects starting in late 2025 are not yet included here.

This increase could be explained by several factors. On the one hand, the European Commission has strongly supported the funding of citizen science for over a decade. On the other hand, organisations were able to build up experience and credibility in citizen science through securing and using regional funding. International funding applications benefit greatly from a strong track record in citizen science. The rise in regional project funding as of 2017 may therefore have contributed to the peak in international funding in 2024. Regional support thus acts as an accelerator for citizen science in Belgium, by increasing success rates in European calls.

Conclusions and recommendations

Belgium has successfully created a stimulating environment for citizen science. Flanders in particular is benefiting from a deliberate policy decision for citizen science as a strategic lever. As a result, initiators from different levels of society have been able to professionalise the funding, development, implementation and valorisation of citizen science. In Europe, Belgium is now recognised as a hotspot for innovative citizen science: the approach is being introduced successfully in strategically chosen domains, initiators increasingly succeed to leverage their experience and strong reputation to secure competitive European funding, and both policy and the economy are increasingly characterised by data-driven decision-making grounded in citizen science.

These achievements demonstrate that explicit policy commitment to citizen science works, and that it pays off on multiple fronts. We have built a broad, innovative and effective citizen science landscape, as evidenced by this second edition of the Citizen Science Scan. Maintaining this momentum is essential, so that science and innovation can continue to benefit from these long-term investments. Scivil will continue to contribute as a facilitator, advisor, promoter and matchmaker for citizen science in Flanders and Belgium.

Recommendations for research funders

- Provide flexible funding channels that explicitly allow citizen science. Align these channels with the interdisciplinary and societal nature of the projects. For example, provide opportunities for projects to allocate personnel and operational costs to tasks that are crucial for a successful citizen science approach, such as communication and community management, or materials and compensation for individual citizens and for non-academic partners in the project.
- Strengthen structural funding. This enables successful projects to keep growing beyond their initial phase. Rather than repeatedly restarting new project cycles, expertise can be maintained and long-term impact becomes possible.
- Invest in infrastructure and professionalisation. Provide resources for data platforms and the development of ethical frameworks tailored to citizen science. This support enhances the reliability and reusability of citizens' contributions.

Recommendations for government policy makers

- Continue investing in strong regional funding. In doing so, projects can build the experience they need for international applications. By strengthening this role, a robust learning environment is created that can further support the rising trend in European successes.
- Consider using citizen science data in policy domains such as climate, biodiversity, well-being, mobility, and living environment. Actively incorporating citizen-generated data into policy processes leads to broader support and greater societal relevance.
- Encourage more collaboration between citizen science and education. This way, pupils gain access to real research practices, and researchers gain access to highly motivated participants.
- Stimulate community-led initiatives. These projects can respond quickly, flexibly and with precision to local needs and communities that are difficult to reach.
- Monitor citizen participation and its impact on citizens themselves through surveys such as the 'Wetenschapsbarometer'. This helps us understand how participation influences the attitudes of citizens towards science. Regular monitoring reveals trends in trust in science and helps tailor support to the needs of the field.
- Ensure that citizen science can also flourish in French-speaking Belgium. Provide regional budgets to build a supportive citizen science infrastructure, following the example of Flanders.

Recommendations for policy makers within organisations

- Provide central support for staff who want to start a citizen science project. Lowering barriers increases the likelihood that new initiatives will become sustainably embedded in your organisation.
- Integrate citizen science into your organisational strategy. Explicitly anchor participatory methods in policy documents and internal processes. This creates an environment where collaboration with citizens becomes more natural.

- Invest in capacity building for citizen science. Strengthen the internal knowledge and visibility of citizen science. Share inspiring examples and give staff access to trainings on participation and co-creation. This creates a broader foundation of competencies that benefits projects in the long term.

Recommendations for (potential) initiators

- Engage citizens beyond data collection. Integrate citizen participation from the very start of the project. Involving citizens in shaping research questions, designing protocols or developing communication not only improves data quality, but also fosters motivation and sustained engagement. Test your approach thoroughly before large-scale rollout, to refine participation materials, methods and instructions. A strong pilot phase leads to more reliable and accessible results for a broader public.
- Make your project visible and share results and collected data through open data. This increases the impact of your initiative and inspires other ongoing projects and potential initiators.
- Consider collaborating with schools. This way, you will access motivated participants and a wide reach within local communities. Furthermore, it is a valuable opportunity to familiarise young people with scientific methods.
- Actively promote diversity and inclusion. Keep barriers low, use clear and accessible language and offer multiple ways for citizens to contribute. Also consider looking for partners in other regions of Belgium. A diverse group of participants makes the data richer and enhances the relevance of the project in society.

About Scivil

Scivil builds bridges for better citizen science. As the Flemish knowledge and research centre for citizen science, Scivil is a catalyst and matchmaker, bringing together all parties and required tools for strong citizen science projects. Scivil promotes, connects, supports and innovates citizen science.

Vision

Scivil wants citizens, scientists and societal actors to solve scientific issues and societal problems together more often, thus optimally matching the acquired knowledge to all stakeholders.

Through citizen science, citizens, scientists and societal actors can collaborate on outstanding and effective scientific research. Moreover, citizens thus learn to think more nuanced and critical about science and experience its importance, both for society and for their personal lives.

Mission

Scivil builds bridges for better citizen science, between (potential) initiators and partners. Scivil is a catalyst and matchmaker, bringing together all parties and required tools, in Flanders and beyond, for strong citizen science projects.

Scivil offers:

- [Workshops and lectures](#) on citizen science tailored to your organisation;
- [Personalised advice](#) on future and ongoing citizen science projects;
- [Networking events](#) to connect citizen science actors;
- [Guides and manuals](#) on partial aspects of citizen science;
- [An innovative](#) citizen science [approach](#) as a partner in your project.

Scivil
Citizen Science
Vlaanderen

www.scivil.be/en

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Survey

The survey below was sent to all projects in the inventory for which contact details were available.

Survey - Inventarisation of Belgian citizen science projects - 2025

As the Flemish Knowledge Centre for Citizen Science, Scivil wants to keep its finger on the pulse of the Flemish Citizen Science landscape. Additionally, as part of a master thesis UCLouvain is working on a study of French speaking citizen science projects in Belgium. We joined forces to create our second inventory of Belgian citizen science projects. In collaboration with students we created a first list of projects over the summer. We would like to deepen this rich dataset of projects in order to gain a better understanding of the number and types of citizen science projects being rolled out in Belgium. By completing the survey below about your project, you will help us take a big step forward. Completing the survey takes about 5 minutes.

Perhaps you already completed this questionnaire during our inventory in 2023. If so, please fill it out again! We would very much like to include your project(s) in the inventory again.

Thank you in advance!

Contact details: info@scivil.be and www.scivil.be/en

What is citizen science?

Citizen science is scientific research conducted in whole or in part by non-scientists (citizens), often in collaboration with or under the guidance of professional scientists. Find out more at <https://www.scivil.be/en/book/citizen-science-something-me>
Interested to read the results of the previous Citizen Science Scan? You can read the report here: <https://www.scivil.be/citizen-science-scan-2023>

General information

Name of the project:

Project website (URL):

In case the project does not have its own website, you can refer to an external website, platform or article in which the project is mentioned

Start year of the project:

End year of the project (if applicable):

Status of the project:

- Active
- Inactive / Completed

Languages in which the project is/was available:

- Dutch
- French
- German
- English
- Other:

Project partners and funding

Lead organisation:

Is this a Belgian organisation?

Does the lead organisation have a branch or registered office in Belgium?

- Yes
- No

Which category fits best with the lead organisation?

- Governmental organisation
- Not-for-profit organisation
- Private organisation

Is the lead organisation a research-performing organisation?

Is conducting research part of the main activities of this organisation?

- Yes
- No

Are there other partners involved in the project?
If yes, which type?

- Research-performing organisation
- Policy (local, regional, national, international)
- Not-for-profit organisations (NGOs, civil movements, CSOs, ...)
- Companies (SMEs, industry, ...)
- Educational organisations and/or schools
- Cultural organisations (libraries, museums, ...)
- Unincorporated group or association
- Other:

Please provide the name of any Belgian partner(s) involved in the project:

What is the main source of funding for the project?

- International project funding
- Federal Belgian project funding
- Regional project funding (Brussels, Flanders, Wallonia)
- Local project funding (cities and municipalities, province)
- Crowdfunding / financial contribution of citizens
- Funded on in-kind contributions of partner organisations
- Sponsoring or private organisations
- Other:

Specify the main source of funding (e.g. FWO, King Baudouin Foundation, own resources, ...):

What is the geographical distribution of the participants participating in the project?

Geographical reach of the project:

- Global (worldwide)
- International (multiple countries)
- National (Belgium)
- Regional (Regions or communities)
- One or more cities or municipalities
- Specific neighbourhoods

Total number of citizens involved?

- 1-20
- 21-100
- 101-500
- 501-1,000
- 1,001-5,000
- 5,000+

Do you know the exact number of participants (taking part until now)? If so, please fill it in below.

Topic of the citizen science project

What is the main scientific theme to which the project contributes?

- Archaeology, History, Heritage
- Biodiversity and Biology
- Computer and Information sciences
- Economy
- Geography: GIS, Cartography
- Geology, Palaeontology
- Engineering
- Climate research
- Art and Culture
- Agriculture and Horticulture
- Environment: Noise pollution
- Environment: Light pollution
- Environment: Air quality
- Environment: Water quality
- Environment: Litter or plastic pollution
- Mobility
- Physics, Math and Astronomy
- Psychology and Educational sciences
- Sociology and Demography
- Language and Literature
- Health and Medical sciences
- Other:

What other scientific topics does the project contribute to, in a secondary way?

- Archaeology, History, Heritage
- Biodiversity and Biology
- Computer and Information sciences
- Economy
- Geography: GIS, Cartography
- Geology, Palaeontology
- Engineering
- Climate research
- Art and Culture
- Agriculture and Horticulture
- Environment: Noise pollution
- Environment: Light pollution
- Environment: Air quality
- Environment: Water quality
- Environment: Litter or plastic pollution
- Mobility
- Physics, Math and Astronomy
- Psychology and Educational sciences
- Sociology and Demography
- Language and Literature
- Health and Medical sciences
- Other:

Briefly describe what scientific activity(ies) the citizens carry out in the project?

In which way(s) do participants contribute to the project?

- Defining research questions
- Shaping the design or intervention through a co-creation process
- Data collection: e.g. executing a scientific protocol with multiple steps, measuring with sensors, counting or identifying, providing data, filling out a questionnaire, taking a sample, ...
- Data analysis: e.g. annotating, transcribing or interpreting data
- Communication and dissemination: e.g. formulating recommendations, communicating results
- Other:

Does the participation take place online or offline?

- Full online participation
- Partial online, partial offline participation
- Full offline participation

Does the project collaborate with schools?

- Yes
- No

A few last questions

May we contact you for an in-depth discussion as part of this study?

- Yes
- No

Would you like to be kept informed about the results of this study?

- Yes
- No

What email address can we contact you at? (for results and/or in-depth discussion)

Finally, would you like to share any other comments or feedback with us?

Appendix 2: Overview of analysed projects

The full dataset of the inventory is available online at <https://www.scivil.be/en/citizen-science-scan>

- (Bij)vangsten in selectieve lokvallen
- AcceleROB
- Action Towards Reducing Aquatic snail-borne Parasitic diseases (ATRAP)
- Aerial and Airing
- ALFAwetlands
- amai!
- Analyse van de personeelsdossiers van koloniale ambtenaren
- Analytische inventarisatie van de boekhoudkundige registers en bewijsstukken van het kasteel van Mirwart (15de-18de eeuw)
- ArchiSols
- ArtGenetics
- Association ELI-S
- Atlas de la biodiversité communale
- BeBirds
- Beetlehangers
- BELpREG zwangerschapsregister
- Be-Music
- Bernache du Canada
- Best practice model voor burgerparticipatie in het beheer van gezondheidsdata
- Beware & Note
- BioAgora
- Biodiversiteit in kaart brengen via Waarnemingen.be
- BioFutures Living Lab
- Blue Zone
- BMH-PFAS
- Bodemvalonderzoek
- BrusselAVenir
- Bruss'Help telling
- BUGS: Benefits of Urban Green Spaces
- ¿Burgerpraat!
- Buurtnatuur.be
- Buzzwatch
- CAIRE
- CamerAI
- Cap biodiversité
- Carcasses de sanglier
- Carcasses d'oiseaux
- CegeSoma - Wikibase Verzet
- CITREE Gent (City Tree Citizen Science)
- CLIMAS
- CoastSnap Belgium
- COLLECT – Citizen Observation of Local Litter in Coastal ECosysTems
- Communities Against Violence
- COR-DNA-project
- Craywatch
- DASA
- Database Akten West-Vlaanderen
- De Grote Tuinvogeltelling
- De invloed van levensstijl op het ontwikkelen van tinnitusklachten
- De Meetnetten
- De Oorzaak
- De Strandwerkgroep België
- Demogen Leuven
- Demogen Visu
- Dialectloket
- Dieren onder de wielen
- DigHiMapper
- Digitale ontsluiting van de arresten van het Hof van assisen Oost-Vlaanderen (1811-1830)
- Digitale ontsluiting van de erfenisaangiften in Oost-Vlaanderen
- Digitale ontsluiting van de erfenisaangiften van het gerechtelijk arrondissement Turnhout
- Digitale ontsluiting vonnissen criminele rechtbank Scheldepartement (Oost-Vlaanderen)
- Digitalisering van de registers van de beraadslagingen van de gemeenteraden en de schepencolleges (1800-1976)
- Digitalisering van het archief van de vzw 'Archives photographiques namuroises'
- DNA-Benelux-project
- DoeDat
- Drinkable Rivers
- Dyle valley (ALFAwetlands Living Lab site)
- Eco Insights
- Ecostrook Hoogmolenbrug
- ELI-S
- ENFORCE
- Enquêtes données d'observations d'espèces
- ERASMOS
- Espèces invasives en Wallonie
- Espèces Natura 2000
- European Ladybird Survey
- European Stag Beetle Monitoring Network
- EuroSense
- Fabrique Ecocitoyenne
- Fietsbarometer

- FlatwormWatch
- Florabank
- FloraBru
- FOURCAST
- FrichNat 2
- From Monitoring to Managing Soil and Water Degradation in Tanzanian Gullies.
- Fuik- en schepnetonderzoek
- Gebruikersrapporten met de KMI smartphone-app
- Gent on Files
- Gentenair
- GezelleBrOn: Guido Gezelles online brieven, een participatieproject
- GMU8 Leuven
- Groene Longen
- Grote Schelpenteldag
- Hals perkament
- HARISSA
- Heeft u een aardbeving gevoeld?
- HER
- Het Grote Vogelweekend
- Hoe paren vissen?
- Houtstookproject
- Huismussentelweekend
- Indexation des registres de population de la province de Namur
- Indexeren notulen gemeenteraad en schepencollege van Aalst en deelgemeenten, 1796-1976
- Indexering van de registers van de burgerlijke stand van de gemeenten van de Duitstalige gemeenschap
- Infectieradar
- InfluencaAir
- InformMe!
- Inventaris van de kabinetsarchieven van de gouverneurs van de provincie Luxemburg
- Inventarisatie van de archieven van het Soevereine Hof van Bouillon
- Inventarisatie van de collectie kaarten en plannen
- IQSW
- Isala-project
- Itinera Nova
- Kapelletjes in Vlaanderen
- Karelvanwijnendaele.be
- Kiekjes van de kermis
- Kleurringen vogels aflezen
- KlimaatTrappers
- Klimaattuiniers
- Kolonietelling (gier)zwaluwen
- Laatste Woorden
- Laboratoire Vivant du Campus Arlon Environnement
- Lentevallen Aziatische hoornaar
- Les chercheurs d'air
- Lichens GO
- LIFE CityTRAQ
- LIKONA
- Lili-app project
- Limburgse werkgroep voor Lichenologie
- Loup
- Luchtpijp
- Maai Mei Niet
- MammalNet
- MapComplete
- MARIN
- Medea
- Meetnet Agrarische Soorten (MAS)
- Meld je strandvondst
- Merovinger DNA
- Microcapteurs
- Mijn Tuinlab
- Missing Maps
- MOMENT-GPS
- MonitAnt
- Monitoring van het visbestand in de Schelde en de Rupel
- MortselAir
- MuggenSurveillance
- Nachtvlindermeetnet
- Natuur-inbouw
- NEST
- Notarius
- Numérisation et indexation des archives photographiques namuroises (1865-2022)
- ODIS
- Onder de Radar
- OneStop living labs
- Ontwikkeling, implementatie en evaluatie van een gedragsinterventie ter verbetering van communicatie over palliatieve zorg tussen personen met kanker en hun arts
- Op zoek naar invasieve klauwkickers
- OpenStreetMap Belgium
- PID 2.0
- Planet Hunters TESS
- Plastic Pirates Belgium
- PLONS
- POEMBAKterie
- POL
- Post entry surveillance of the oriental fruit fly
- Project Spintmijt
- Punt Transect Telling (PTT)

- Radio Meteor Zoo
- Recreatieve Zeevisserij
- Registers van de vogelcollectie van het AfrikaMuseum
- Registry of insects of the AfricaMuseum
- Registry of the tree samples of the AfricaMuseum
- Repair Together ASBL
- River Watchers
- S.O.S. Antwerpen
- Salamandre et Tritons
- SAPEX (Citizen science, experimental archaeology, and plant working)
- Saving Private Orion
- Schermenonderzoek
- School op de Teller
- Score
- SeaWatch-B
- Small world of words
- Smarts
- Smartwater
- Social Purrspectives Kattenonderzoek
- SoleWay
- Spartacus
- SPIN-CITY
- Spinicornis
- Spoon - Food Systems in transition
- Sport en recreatie-activiteiten als middel voor rookpreventie bij kwetsbare jongeren: ontwikkelen en testen van een nieuwe preventie-aanpak voor jongeren die moeilijk te bereiken zijn.
- STAGE Horizon EU
- Steenuil
- Straatvinken
- Street Poems
- Suivi hérisson
- SuRiPest
- TekenNet - TiquesNet
- Tellingen Aangespoelde Vogels
- Telraam
- Teste ton sol
- TESTEREP
- TETTRIs: Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations
- Titan
- Titicaca Aqua Watch
- Together4Water
- Trekvogeltelling
- Truffulales
- Truienair
- Urban ReLeaf
- Urbaan mezenproject
- Valley of the Zuidleie (ALFAwetlands Living Lab site)
- Val-u-Sun
- Van enkele zaadcellen tot oude menselijke resten
- Van Monitoring tot Restoratie van Bodem- en Waterdegradatie door Geulerosie in Tanzania
- Van omstaander tot held
- Van ontwerp tot weefsel: kleurrijk achter de schermen!
- VanHarte (CS-Heart)
- Verzamel muggeneitjes en -larven in je tuin!
- VespaWatch
- ViadkuKaduk Meetactie
- Vierkante meter: Iedereen archeoloog!
- VISAVIS
- Vleermuizen op (kerk)zolders
- Vogelatlas
- Vogels onder hoogspanning in België
- VOSS
- Vroege detectie en verwijdering van schadelijke algenbloeien
- Vyakulani Diaspora Women
- Waarschuwingssysteem Invasieve Exoten
- Watervogels
- Wekelijkse Vlindertelling
- Wekelijkse vogeltelling
- Werkgroep Bryologie en Lichenologie
- Westhoek Verbeeldt
- Wilder
- WOW-BE
- Zeldzame dieren
- Zichtbaar Grondwater
- Zitten er teken in jouw tuin?
- Zwarte Beek (ALFAwetlands Living Lab site)